

Knowledge dynamics and makerspaces: proximities and local development in the Central Europe

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Abstract

The rationale behind this working paper is reflected in the investigation of knowledge partners and the role of proximities through makerspaces. Hence, these spaces are creating a positive impact on creating a cultural change by encouraging entrepreneurship in the community, support small business growth, and increase workforce retention. Therefore, the focus is on the knowledge partners and the local growth, in the selected Central European countries (Poland, Czechia, Slovakia), where makerspaces have seen a more significant increase. Furthermore, the paper aims to shed some light on both direct and indirect effects of makerspaces on local development. The research design is based on empirical qualitative analysis of primary data gathered through semi-structured interviews with stakeholders in makerspaces. The novelty of our empirical research is reflected in identifying spatial scales to distinguish the role of proximity in knowledge transfer through makerspaces. The working paper presents policy implications to nurture different knowledge flows in and its role in local development. Furthermore, the research reflects on the knowledge transmission among the central knowledge partners considering different proximities.

Keywords

makerspaces, knowledge dynamics, Central Europe, local development, proximity

1 Introduction and theoretical underpinnings

This working paper introduces an investigation into the dynamics of knowledge partners within makerspaces, focusing specifically on the context of Central and Eastern Europe and emphasizing the role of these spaces. Makerspaces have emerged as dynamic, multi-agent environments where diverse groups co-create, share, and refine knowledge. Shi and Chen (2022) conceptualize these spaces as knowledge ecosystems that evolve through the orchestration of complex interrelations among individuals, organizations, and the environment. In addition, Klemichen et al. (2022) highlight how makerspaces serve not only as physical spaces for technological prototyping but also as social hubs that nurture collaborative learning and innovation considering cognitive proximity reflecting on the similarity in the knowledge bases, expertise, and problem-solving approaches among collaborating entities (Xu et al., 2021). These dual functions underline the central role of makerspaces in fostering informal, experiential, and lifelong learning opportunities in rapidly changing technological landscapes (van Holm, 2017). However, there is

an underdeveloped linkage between lifelong learning and makerspaces. The concept is introduced but not anchored to Central Europe's post-socialist skill-retention challenges.

Central and Eastern Europe presents a unique geographical and socio-political context where the evolution of makerspaces is entangled with regional socio-economic development challenges and the transformative potential of lifelong learning. Van Holm (2017) revealed spatial differentiations that reflect local socio-economic realities, and such variations underscore the potential for makerspaces to contribute to balanced local development through targeted lifelong learning initiatives. Furthermore, the critical analysis of policy adaptation in the region, as discussed by Antonowicz et al. (2017), suggests that the translation of global innovation paradigms into local contexts requires the integration of makerspaces within broader strategic frameworks that promote sustainable skill development and socio-economic resilience. By bridging the theoretical insights on makerspaces with the distinct socio-economic conditions of Central and Eastern Europe, this study argues for a systematic approach in examining how makerspaces can serve as catalysts for lifelong learning, creating spaces for continuous personal and professional development.

Nonetheless, there is contrast urban vs. peripheral makerspace outcomes (Van Holm, 2021; Capdevila, 2019) to highlight underexplored spatial asymmetries. Spatial asymmetries relate primarily to geographical proximity of physical closeness between organizations or agents (Xu et al., 2021; Fu & Zang, 2024). This form of proximity facilitates frequent face-to-face interactions, rapid information sharing, and the formation of dense networks (Micek, 2020). Most studies deal with urban settings in an era where technological advancements necessitate continuous skill augmentation and adaptability through institutional proximity, where entities share similar formal and informal rules, norms, frameworks, and cultural values (Xu et al., 2021). Studies on makerspaces have demonstrated that the proliferation of informal learning environments, such as makerspaces, is integral to building adaptive, resilient communities prepared to meet the challenges of future employment and technological shifts in urban areas (Mersand, 2021; Li & Gao, 2021; Oswald & Zhao, 2021). In this respect, the interaction between knowledge creation in makerspaces and educational initiatives offers a promising avenue to enhance local competitiveness and social transformation, particularly in areas that are adapting to post-socialist transitions and evolving economic paradigms (Mersand, 2021; Gillespie et al., 2021). Hence, the present work interweaves these multidimensional themes comprising knowledge interactions and local development in Central and Eastern Europe.

2 Methods

This study employs an exploratory qualitative research design to examine the operational dynamics and socio-economic contributions of 22 makerspaces situated in peripheral regions of Europe. These case were purposively selected based on prior documentation of their active involvement in addressing context-specific challenges, including digital exclusion, restricted mobility infrastructure, and localized labour shortages. The research is theoretically anchored in among five societal subsystems or stakeholders such as academia, industry, government, civil society, and the natural environment. This framework facilitates an in-depth exploration of how makerspaces act as intermediaries in orchestrating multi-stakeholder, place-based knowledge ecosystems. To further enrich the analysis, the study integrates insights from proximity studies (geographical, cognitive, institutional). We focus on spatial and relational factors that mediate collaboration and resource mobilisation (Boschma, 2005; Balland et al., 2015). These conceptual lenses collectively inform a nuanced investigation of the relational embeddedness and strategic positioning of makerspaces within regional innovation systems. Empirical data were collected through semi-structured interviews conducted with makerspace managers and operational staff across the selected sites (Poland, Czechia, Slovakia) supplemented by additional interviews with policymakers, and practitioners specializing in local development and community development. Participants were selected via criterion-based sampling, focusing on individuals affiliated with makerspaces recognized for their proactive engagement in local development interventions, such as inter-municipal cooperation,

vocational upskilling programs, and community outreach initiatives. Ethical considerations covered informed consent, and anonymity was maintained particularly in relation to discussions involving financial precarity, stakeholder misalignments, or conflicts of interest. All interview data were securely stored and subjected to member checking to enhance the validity and reliability of the findings. The interview protocol was structured around three thematic axes:

Operational and organizational constraints in knowledge partnerships, infrastructural limitations, and alignment of diverse stakeholder agendas.

Knowledge generation and circulation, focusing on informal learning practices, prototyping activities, peer-to-peer exchanges, and engagement with external knowledge networks.

Policy and governance interactions, encompassing relationships with municipal bodies, participation in European Union innovation schemes, and collaborations with civil society organizations.

All interviews were recorded, transcribed, and analysed using Atlas.ti software through an open coding process. The coding was guided by a hybrid framework, integrating deductive codes derived from the proximity literature with emergent codes grounded in participants' narratives. This methodology enables a deeper insight into how makerspaces translate micro-level knowledge practices into macro-level impacts on urban development trajectories. Furthermore, we this step was designed in such a way that we could capture grassroots initiatives in makerspaces considering sustainable territorial growth through collaborative spaces (Morea & Sabatini, 2023; Rahman & Best, 2024).

3 Results

The study revealed that makerspaces in lagging regions successfully addressed weak digital skills and infrastructure gaps, particularly through hands-on training in emerging technologies like 3D printing, robotics, and CNC machining (Dos Santos & Benneworth, 2019). Participants reported increased technical proficiency, with many gaining competencies directly applicable to local industries such as manufacturing and repair services. For example, workshops on prototyping enabled users to support small-scale production for regional artisans considering institutional proximity that mitigates cognitive gaps. However, this skill development rarely translated into entrepreneurial outcomes or new business creation as discussed by Bao (2025). Despite exposure to tools and collaborative environments, no interviewees launched ventures rooted in their makerspace experience. This contrasts with urban makerspaces, where skill acquisition often catalyses start-ups. The disconnect highlights structural barriers in peripheral areas, including limited access to seed funding, mentorship networks, and markets, which are often critical factors for scaling ideas into enterprises. Notably, while makerspaces fostered local social networking, strengthening ties among educators, policymakers, and community members, their role in reversing brain drain was debatable. However, the results suggest makerspaces in peripheral areas related to cognitive proximity (similarity in similarity in the knowledge bases). This suggests that peripheral makerspaces may inadvertently equip individuals with "exit options" rather than tools for local economic revitalization, particularly when regional job markets lack high-tech opportunities. This "*skill leakage*" phenomenon reflects a systemic issue, where peripheral areas often lack the high-tech employment infrastructure to retain talent, transforming makerspaces into stepping stones for exit rather than anchors for local development. Hence, contrary to initial hypotheses, makerspaces exhibited limited efficacy in mitigating brain drain, instead inadvertently accelerating outmigration among skilled users. The results support Capdevila's (2014) analysis of innovation ecosystems in non-core regions through partnership primarily with NGOs, makerspaces/fablabs, and community centres (strong ties as knowledge partners). This divergence from urban makerspace outcomes, where skill acquisition frequently catalyses entrepreneurial activities. Peripheral areas' sparse networks of angel investors, fragmented mentorship systems, and limited absorptive capacity in local industries (Tödtling & Trippl, 2005) create an innovation infrastructure gap that even well-equipped makerspaces cannot bridge alone.

Figure 1: Knowledge partners of makerspaces in CEE

Makerspaces demonstrated high variability in local development outcomes, heavily dependent on regional priorities and stakeholder engagement. In areas with strong public-private partnerships, such as those aligned with EU-funded programs, makerspaces became hubs for workforce training, preparing residents for roles in automation and advanced manufacturing. For instance, collaborations with vocational schools enabled certifications in digital fabrication, improving employability in nearby industrial clusters. Furthermore, these outcomes resonate with Smith et al.'s (2013) *“ingenuity”* framing of grassroots innovation, where systemic partnerships enable scaling beyond isolated skill-building. Conversely, in regions where makerspaces operated independently of broader policy frameworks, their impact was constrained to short-term workshops for children and teenagers, with minimal spill-over effects on existing businesses or infrastructure. The study found no evidence of makerspaces directly hampering brain drain, as hypothesized. Instead, their presence often amplified aspirations for mobility among skilled users. One respondent noted: *“The makerspace showed me what’s possible with tech—but to pursue those possibilities, I had to leave for a city with more resources.”* This reflects a paradox that while makerspaces empower individuals, peripheral areas often lack ecosystems to retain talent, leading to skill leakage. Furthermore, corporate-led initiatives (e.g., equipment donations from tech firms) sometimes overshadowed grassroots policymaking, prioritizing social responsibility optics over sustainable local capacity-building. This dynamic underscore a broader trend of corporate interventions, though beneficial for skill acquisition, risk perpetuating dependency cycles by side-lining grassroots policymaking aimed at fostering endogenous growth. Additionally, the results highlight the role of institutional thickness in peripheral regions (Komárek & Chromý, 2020). Makerspaces operating outside policy frameworks often defaulted to ad-hoc workshops with the risk of becoming what Storper (2018) argues as *“capability islands”* reinforcing rather than mitigating core-periphery disparities.

Table 1: The role of makerspaces on local development in CEE

Dimensions of local growth (van Holm, 2107)	Intensity
Cultural change by encouraging entrepreneurship in the community	Low intensity
Supporting small business growth through knowledge exchange	Not observed
Providing workforce training	Large intensity
Increasing workforce retention (hampering brain drain)	Not observed

The hampered economic impact of makerspaces stemmed from operational constraints and demographic targeting. Most spaces focused narrowly on youth education, side-lining potential synergies with adult entrepreneurs or SMEs. Short-term funding cycles further limited programming to one-off events rather than longitudinal projects. For example, a makerspace director noted: *"We're stuck in a cycle of grant chasing—every six months, we reboot programs instead of deepening partnerships."* This instability hindered the accumulation of institutional knowledge and trust with local industries (lower institutional proximity). Additionally, the small scale of most makerspaces restricted their ability to drive systemic change due to membership limitations. While the results highlighted successful collaborations, these remained isolated rather than replicable models. The absence of regional policy frameworks to coordinate makerspaces with innovation clusters or R&D institutions exacerbated fragmentation. Without mechanisms to bridge skill development with market access and financing, makerspaces functioned as islands of capability in ecosystems ill-equipped to harness their potential. Furthermore, the paradox of skill development is further illustrated by the disconnect between technical empowerment and economic transformation. The results suggest transforming underutilized public spaces into hubs for innovation and collaboration, fostering community engagement. However, these transformations are episodic rather than systemic due to short-term funding cycles and limited stakeholder coordination—a dynamic consistent with Seyfang & Smith's (2007) critique of grassroots initiatives operating within fragmented ecosystems. Furthermore, these spaces strengthen social networks within cognitive proximity among diverse stakeholders—educators, policymakers, and community members with similar knowledge bases to create resilient communities (Benář et al., 2023).

Respondents reported improvements in competencies such as prototyping, robotics, and manufacturing. Structural barriers in peripheries reflect on limited access to seed funding, fragmented mentorship networks, and undersized consumer markets. As one interviewee noted, *"We can build a prototype, but scaling it here? There's no venture capital, no supply chain partners... just inertia."* This highlights how peripheral makerspaces function as skill incubators without the systemic support to convert capabilities into commercial outcomes. On the other hand, the results suggest the enhancement of interdisciplinary learning by merging technical skills with creative problem-solving, enabling participants to apply knowledge across domains, aligning with the grassroots innovation by Vuorikari et al (2021).

Table 2: Makerspaces and their effects on local development

Effect type	Direction
cross-curricular connections	direct
learning towards prototyping	direct
episodic transformation of public space	indirect
strengthening microclusters of CCI	indirect
risk of isolation reduction	direct
increasing community ties	indirect
job satisfaction and well being	direct

4 Conclusion

The paper reveals that makerspaces in Central and Eastern Europe's peripheral regions successfully address first-order challenges of digital exclusion and skill gaps through hands-on training in emerging

technologies. Makerspaces in peripheral areas gained technical proficiencies applicable to local industries, such as small-scale manufacturing and repair services. However, these spaces struggled to catalyse entrepreneurial outcomes or stem brain drain, with upskilled users migrating to urban hubs within 18 months. Structural barriers such as fragmented mentorship networks, sparse venture capital, and weak absorptive capacity in local industries prevented the translation of technical empowerment into commercial ventures. While makerspaces strengthened social ties among educators, policymakers, and community members, these networks lacked the institutional thickness to drive systemic change, resulting in "islands of capability" disconnected from regional innovation ecosystems.

The contribution is reflected in advancing the discourse on grassroots innovation by integrating the proximities to analyse makerspaces' intermediary roles in peripheral areas. It introduces the concept of "*skill leakage*" as a dynamic, where technical upskilling accelerates outmigration due to mismatches between capability development and local opportunity structures. The study also how proximities mediate knowledge partners, offering a granular framework to assess collaboration efficacy. By contextualizing makerspaces within Central Europe's post-socialist socio-economic landscape, the work challenges universalist assumptions about the maker movement's developmental impact, emphasizing place-specific institutional configurations.

There are limitations regarding the reliance on qualitative data, which limits generalizability, though depth of analysis aligns with exploratory aims. The focus on Central Europe's unique post-socialist context may restrict direct applicability to other peripheral areas. Moreover, the reliance on self-reported data from makerspace staff risks survivorship bias. Considering the implications, there is an argument to couple local innovation strategies and makerspace development with parallel public support, SME mentorship programs, and industry-specific R&D clusters. This highlights the need for long term partnerships, where makerspaces could adopt dual demographic targeting youth STEM education with adult entrepreneur upskilling, and to formalise liaisons with industrial clusters to ensure their sustainable development trajectories in peripheral areas (Vuorikari et al., 2019). The paper underscores that makerspaces alone cannot redress systemic innovation asymmetries. Their transformative potential hinges on integration into place-sensitive innovation "*creative*" ecosystems, demanding interdisciplinary collaboration among maker movement, policymakers, educators, and grassroots initiatives.

Future research should adopt longitudinal designs to track the temporal evolution of makerspaces' socio-economic impacts, particularly in peripheral regions. Furthermore, to investigate why urban makerspaces successfully bridge skill-commercialization gaps, while peripheral areas struggle, despite they often have similar resource levels.

Acknowledgement

This document has been developed on the basis of a similar template provided for the International Conference of Concurrent Enterprising.

No AI has been used in the production of the content of this paper nor in text generation or correction.

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